

THE ROLE OF IMPORTANTCE ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN THEINTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

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Abstract: This article is about the global importance of English language, its place in the past and present and how important it is for present and future generation. As social beings human beings need to communicate to each other communication is very important because everything is impossible to be done without communication. Nowadays in the global era communication has become one of the most crucial elements. The study was under taken to understand the importance of English language in present scenario.

Key words: Global importance, communication, international level, language, speaking, opportunities.

Introduction: Language is our primary source of communication .It is the method through which we share our ideas and thoughts with others. There are thousands of language in the world. Every country has their own national language in addition to a variety of local languages spoken and understand by their people in different regions some languages are spoken by millions of people and others by only a few thousand. In global world the importance of English cannot be denied and ignored since English is the most common language spoken everywhere. English is one of the most used language in the world. Even outside of countries like the USE and the UK, many people can speak and understand English. If you include people who speak it as a second language, an estimated 1 billion people worldwide speak English. On top of this, 67 countries have English as their official language and there are 27 countries that have English as their secondary official language. Through out the countries the British Empire expanded and ruled over many different countries including most of the ones just mentioned and many more. In many cases, the British forced the people they ruled over to speak English

and some of these countries still speak English ,even if it is not their main language .People often talk about English as a global language. With more than 350 million people around the world speaking English as a first language and more than 430 million speaking it as a second language, there are English speakers in most countries around the world. English may not be the most spoken language in the world, but it is the official language 53 countries and spoken by around 400 million people across the globe. English is not just about being able to communicate with native English speakers, it is the most common second language in the world.Currently, English is the primary language of not only countries actively touched by British imperialism, but also many business and cultural spheres dominated by those countries. As such, It is a useful and even necessary language to know. Learning English is important and people all over the world decide to study it as a second language. Many counties include English as a second language in their school syllabus and children start learning English at a young age. English is the language of science, of aviation, computers, diplomacy and tourism. Knowing English increases your chances of getting a good job in a multinational company.English is the dominant or official language in a number of countries, including many former British Empire territories. The rise of the British Empire offers many clues as to why the English language is so popular. People often want to know the best language to learn to great in life.Many think that learning English, the international language, is the best option. English is of course an excellent choice.It is not enough to want to be fluent in English. In order to actually learn English, you have to like learning English.

ENGLISH OPENS NEW CAREER OPPORTUNITIES

First and foremost, learning English can help you pursue and obtain more career opportunities. These days, the job market is global many companies need employees who can communicate English. By learning English, you could become a translator, a language teacher or an English marketing professional for a global company.Learning English is an important step forward to all of your goals.

ENGLISH IS THE TOP LANGUAGE OF THE INTERNET

English is the most used language online, with nearly 1 billion users typing and chatting in the language. If you can understand and read English you will be able to access and enjoy more resources online and you can read world news, participate in a discussion on a forum. If you can understand English you will be able to communicate with more people online and use many more materials. The possibilities are endless. Learning English will open a whole world of entertainment for you. It is hard to image a young person nowadays who does not speak or study at least one language besides their mother tongue. Globalization forces so many people to communicate and cooperate more in a variety of business. But every language is important. It depends on the situation .you need a world language to communicate with people around the world without learning their regional language. English is the world language and it helps you everywhere.

SKILLS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE

English has four skills that are listening, speaking, reading and writing. ‘To speak is to listen and to write is to read.’ Without the integration between these four skills, English will be clueless. In our Egyptian environment, students believe that English only consists of two main parts that are Grammar and Vocabulary (it is reading and writing). Even the educational system supports this notion through dull curricula, teaching methods and exams that only measure reading and writing. When students come to TOEFL or IELTS, they do fail in the very critical skills which are speaking and listening. These skills are going to help them pass tests like TOEFL or IELTS to apply for abroad universities after graduation or working in industry where English is mainly used. In addition to inspiring students with the language that will help them exchange experiences with other people from different cultures through the social media and support students of practical colleges like medicine or geometry where English is the study language.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion: The importance of English cannot be denied. English is an international language in the world. Most people are using this language on the daily life. It is an important language because we use this language to

communication with other countries people. English is a common language and you can use English to become an international person. In this global era the people are urged to be able to communicate globally. English language plays a very important role especially in international communication. By mastering in English people will able to learn more knowledge and gather more information. English helps people to get jobs in globalization use English as major priority. English to make finding job easier and a major skill which make the category of the applicant be considered at the high quality as a qualified applicant and the skill will carry the applicants to get a good job in a high position in national and international profession.

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